

Complexation Study of Cadmium with a Schiff Base Vanillin Trisbuffer

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Manuscript received 19 September 1977, accepted 7 July 1978

Polarographic study of complexation of cadmium with a Schiff base derived from vanillin and trisbuffer was carried out in DMF-water media of three different compositions (viz. 0%, 30% and 50% v/v of DMF). 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complex species are present in the solution. Overall stability constants were calculated using DeFord and Hume treatment at three different temperatures (viz. 30°, 40° and 50°). Free energy change ΔG , Enthalpy change ΔH and Entropy change ΔS were also calculated for all the three media.

A new, mathematical model, recently developed by Mihailov, to calculate stability constants from \bar{n} values was used to check the data obtained from DeFord and Hume method.

SCHIFF bases are pharmaceutically important compounds. Schiff base complexes of transition metals are studied¹. New Schiff bases are prepared by several workers²; however, polarographic study of Schiff base complexes is limited³. Schiff base complexes of antimony and bismuth have been studied by present authors^{4,5}. Present study deals with the polarographic behaviour of Cd-Vanillin trisbuffer complex in DMF-water media. Three different compositions of the solvents are used viz. 0%v/v; 30% v/v, 50% v/v DMF-water.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. Final concentration of Cd^{2+} was 0.2 mM in 0.1M KNO_3 containing 0.01% gelatin.

Preparation and characteristics of the ligand-Vanillin trisbuffer VT—is reported earlier⁴. Ligand concentration used in the study was varied from 0.005M to 0.25M. The complexation study at all the concentrations of the ligand was made at the original pH of metal ligand solution, i.e., 8.5 ± 0.1 as nature of the ligand is affected by the pH. Polarograms of the metal ions were recorded at 7.5 pH as the ions precipitate above this pH.

Primarily, complexation behaviour was marked by polarograms-obtained on a Elico recording D.C. polarograph type CL 25. Final polarograms were recorded manually⁶ on a Toshniwal polarograph type CLO 2A with Beltronix microammeter.

Oxygen-free nitrogen gas bubbled through the system to remove oxygen in each case. The definite temp. of the system was attained in a Toshniwal temperature bath GL 15 within the accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Capillary characteristics $2.3 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ at 0 voltage, in 0.1M KNO_3 .

Results and Discussion

A single, well defined reduction wave is obtained in each case. Temperature coefficient of the limiting current lies between 1.1% to 1.3% $^\circ\text{C}$. Plot of i_a vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ is straight line. These facts indicate that the limiting current is, diffusion controlled.

The value of number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction—obtained from the ratio of $I/1.6$ —comes out to be 2. The plot of E vs $\log \bar{z}/\bar{z}_a - \bar{z}$ is linear, with a slope⁻¹ of 35 ± 2 mv. This value of the slope suggest 2 electron reversible process.

$E_{1/2}$ values are obtained from traditional log plots. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_x$ is not linear but a smooth curve in all the three systems indicating thereby the presence of more than one complex species.

Method of DeFord and Hume⁷ is utilised to calculate individual stability constants of the complex.

Following relations are used :

$$F_0[X] = \text{antilog} \left\{ \frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_m}{I_0} \right\} \dots (1)$$

$$F_1[X] = \frac{F_0[X] - 1}{[X]} \dots (2)$$

$$F_2[X] = \frac{F_1[X] - \beta_1}{[X]} \dots (3)$$

$$F_3[X] = \frac{F_2[X] - \beta_2}{[X]} \dots (4)$$

where $\Delta E_{1/2}$ is the difference of half-wave potential of

the complex and the simple metal ion. I_m and I_c are the diffusion current constants of the metal ion and the complex respectively.

Plot of $F_0[X]$ vs $[X]$ and $F_1[X]$ vs $[X]$ are smooth curves suggesting thereby presence of complex species higher than 1 : 2 complex. Plot of $F_2[X]$ vs $[X]$ is linear and the plot of $F_3[X]$ vs $[X]$ is linear but parallel to X-axis which suggest existence

of complex species up to 1 : 3 complex in the bulk of the solution.

From intercept of plot $F_1[X]$ vs $[X]$, $F_2[X]$ vs $[X]$, $F_3[X]$ vs $[X]$, β_1 , β_2 and β_3 the stability constants are obtained respectively. Values of functions $F_0[X]$, $F_1[X]$, $F_2[X]$ and $F_3[X]$ for all the three systems are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF VARIOUS FUNCTIONS FOR Cd-VT COMPLEX IN 50% DMF-WATER MEDIUM AT 30°, 40°, 50°.

Ligand con. in M	Temp.°C	$E_{1/2}$ in volts	i_d in div.	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$	$F_3(X)$
0.00	30	0.573	4.6	—	—	—	—
	40	0.571	5.3	—	—	—	—
	50	0.568	6.1	—	—	—	—
0.005	30	0.580	4.4	1.8	160	—	—
	40	0.574	5.3	1.541	108.2	—	—
	50	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.01	30	0.589	4.55	3.45	245	6500	150000
	40	0.5825	5.25	2.372	137.2	3700	—
	50	0.572	6.0	1.36	36.00	—	—
0.02	30	0.599	4.35	7.77	338.5	7925	146000
	40	0.592	5.1	4.94	197.0	4849	—
	50	0.5825	5.85	2.96	98.0	—	—
0.04	30	0.612	4.00	22.96	549.00	9225	106000
	40	0.609	4.95	18.00	425.30	8132.5	84600
	50	0.600	5.7	13.29	307.25	6431.25	53300
0.08	30	0.6355	4.05	137.40	1705.00	19062	176000
	40	0.630	4.95	85.05	1050.63	11822	88400
	50	0.620	5.7	62.44	768.00	8975	58400
0.125	30	0.650	4.0	423.60	3380.00	25600	165000
	40	0.644	4.75	252.69	2013.49	15308	84500
	50	0.6385	5.45	179.00	1424.03	10990	53500
0.25	30	0.674	3.75	2851.00	11400	44800	159000
	40	0.669	4.5	1710.3	6837	26949	88600
	50	0.6635	5.2	1135.86	4539	17958	54600

TABLE 2—VALUES OF VARIOUS FUNCTIONS FOR Cd-VT COMPLEX IN 30% DMF-WATER MEDIUM AT 30°, 40°, 50°.

Ligand con. in M	Temp.°C.	$E_{1/2}$ in volts	i_d in div.	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$	$F_3(X)$
0.0	30	0.571	4.9	—	—	—	—
	40	0.568	5.2	—	—	—	—
	50	0.565	5.6	—	—	—	—
0.005	30	0.5800	4.85	2.0	200.00	—	—
	40	0.5750	5.2	1.682	136.40	—	—
	50	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.01	30	0.5880	4.45	4.0	300.00	—	—
	40	0.5840	4.8	3.55	255.00	—	—
	50	0.5730	5.55	1.78	168.00	—	—
0.02	30	0.5910	4.1	5.436	222.00	—	—
	40	0.5895	4.4	5.86	243.00	3650	22500
	50	0.5820	5.1	3.72	136.00	—	—
0.04	30	0.6065	3.95	18.92	448.00	6700	60000
	40	0.6020	4.35	14.81	345.43	4385	29625
	50	0.5940	5.1	8.83	195.00	1900	18750
0.075	30	0.6210	3.65	62.31	817.47	8500	56000
	40	0.6160	4.05	45.40	592.00	5620	32346
	50	0.6075	4.8	24.84	317.80	2637	19827
0.15	30	0.6420	3.6	316.64	2104.24	12828	56853
	40	0.6360	3.95	202.25	1341.70	7811	30740
	50	0.6290	4.76	108.69	717.93	3986	18907
0.25	30	0.6595	3.6	1213.10	4848.37	18673	57493
	40	0.6530	3.9	721.20	2880.81	10843	30572
	50	0.6460	4.7	404.89	1615.57	5982	19328

TABLE 3—VALUES OF VARIOUS FUNCTIONS FOR Cd-VT COMPLEX IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 30°, 40°, 50°

Ligand con. in M	Temp. °C	$E_{1/2}$ in volts	i_d in div.	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$	$F_3(X)$
0.00	30	0.571	5.8	—	—	—	—
	40	0.568	6.4	—	—	—	—
	50	0.565	7.00	—	—	—	—
0.01	30	0.577	5.8	1.58	58.00	—	—
	30	0.581	5.65	2.21	60.5	1025	—
	40	0.5755	6.25	1.8	40.0	500	7500
0.02	50	0.5700	7.0	1.5	25.0	—	—
	30	0.602	4.85	12.9	148.9	1361	9512
	40	0.5975	6.2	9.16	102.00	900	6875
0.08	50	0.5870	6.5	5.8	60.00	500	3750
	30	0.6295	4.8	67.95	418.44	2362	11012
	40	0.619	6.1	46.34	283.00	1581	7695
0.16	50	0.6085	6.5	25.00	150.00	812	3800
	30	0.6390	4.8	223.28	889.00	3396	11186
	40	0.6345	6.0	149.18	592.5	2250	7600
0.25	50	0.6240	6.4	83.00	328.2	1225	4000

$\beta_3=11100$ at 30°,
 $\beta_3=7500$ at 40°,
 $\beta_3=3800$ at 50°.

Stability constants, Free energy changes, enthalpy changes and entropy changes are given in Tables 1A, 2A and 3A.

by percentage of non-aqueous solvent. It increases linearly with the increase in proportion of DMF.

TABLE 1A—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Cd-VT IN 50% DMF-water medium

Temp. °C	log β_3	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔH° K cal/mole	ΔS° cal/mole
30	5.18	-7.22	-10.22	-9.9
40	4.94	-7.11	-10.22	-9.9
50	4.73	-7.03	-10.22	-9.9

TABLE 2A—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Cd-VT COMPLEX IN 30% DMF-WATER MEDIUM

Temp. °C	log β_3	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔH° K cal/mole	ΔS° cal/mole
30	4.75	-6.62	-10.82	-13.88
40	4.48	-6.45	-10.82	-13.88
50	4.28	-6.36	-10.82	-13.88

TABLE 3A—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Cd-VT COMPLEX IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Temp. °C	log β_3	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔH° K cal/mole	ΔS° cal/mole
30	4.05	-5.67	-10.12	-14.4
40	3.88	-5.59	-10.12	-14.4
50	3.58	-5.82	-10.12	-14.4

The plots of $F_0[X]$, $F_1[X]$, $F_2[X]$ and $F_3[X]$ vs C_x are shown in Fig. 1 for 50% DMF-water system at 50°.

The stability of the complex is strongly affected

Fig. 1 Functions of Cd-VT complex, 50% DMF, 50°.

The values of stability constants are decreasing with increasing temperature showing dissociation of the complex at higher temperatures. ΔH° is negative, which is indicative of exothermic reaction.

For 0% DMF, at 30°, $\beta_1=40$, $\beta_2=600$; at 40°, $\beta_1=30$, $\beta_2=350$; at 50°, $\beta_1=20$, $\beta_2=200$. For 30% DMF, at 30°, $\beta_1=180$, $\beta_2=4300$; at 40°, $\beta_1=170$, $\beta_2=3200$; at 50°, $\beta_1=120$, $\beta_2=1150$. For 50% DMF, at 30°, $\beta_1=180$, $\beta_2=5000$; at 40°, $\beta_1=100$, $\beta_2=4750$; at 50°, $\beta_1=50$, $\beta_2=4300$.

A new mathematical model, recently developed by Mihailov was also used to check the stability constant of the complex in 50% DMF-water medium at 30°.

According to Mihailov⁸

$$\beta_n = A \frac{a^n}{n!} \quad \dots (5)$$

where,

β_n = the overall stability constant,
 n = ligand number attached to metal ion,
 A and a = constants.

On putting $n = 1, 2, 3$, etc., one can get the values for β_1, β_2 and β_3

A and a are obtained by,

$$\bar{n} = A \sum_{n=1}^{n=N} \frac{a^n [L]^n}{(n-1)!} \left\{ 1 + A \sum_{n=1}^{n=N} \frac{a^n}{n!} [L]^n \right\}^{-1} \quad \dots (6)$$

where, N = the maximum coordination number of the metal. $[L]$ = free ligand concentration.

Calculation of \bar{n}

Values of various \bar{n} were obtained from the different slopes of the smooth curve of $\log F_o(X)$ vs $\log [X]$ at different ligand concentrations⁹.

For two different values of $[L]$, we will have two \bar{n} values. Using these values; A and a were calculated.

For Cd-VT complex in 50% DMF-water mixture at 30°. taking $\bar{n} = 0.8$ at $[L] = 0.008M$ and $\bar{n} = 0.625$ at $[L] = 0.005M$, $a = 45.75$ and $A = 5.06$ were found.

Putting values of a and A in eqn. (5).

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_1 &= 232.62, \\ \beta_2 &= 5316.38, \\ \beta_3 &= 81074. \end{aligned}$$

These values are strikingly nearer to the values obtained by DeFord and Hume method (Table 1a) for specific complex species. The degree of formation (α_j) for 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes in 50% DMF-water at 30° were calculated using stability constants derived by DeFord and Hume method and by Mihailov treatment.

$$\alpha_j = \frac{\beta_j [X]^j}{\sum_{n=0}^{n=N} \beta_n [X]^n} \quad \dots (7)$$

The plot of degree of formation α_j obtained from the data of DeFord and Hume and of Mihailov vs $\log C_x$ are shown in Fig. 2 by solid and dotted line. They are in good agreement with each other.

Fig. 2. Distribution curves of Cd-VT complex 50% DMF, 30°
 — DeFord & Hume.
 Mihailov.

The treatment of mathematical model is highly admirable since it is quite simple. It gives detail regarding series of stability constants by one simple equation. In the DeFord and Hume method, extrapolation of the curves is main part of the calculation and hence the slight error in extrapolation may change the data appreciably. Mihailov et al¹⁰ have checked their model for many different metal ligand systems composed of simple ligand. In the present case, an attempt is made to utilise the treatment for more complicated system containing bulky ligand such as VT.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Saurashtra University, Rajkot, for laboratory facilities, and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for Junior Research Fellowship to two of them (T.T. & M.S.P.).

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